

Linkage analysis of a photoperiod-sensitive gene *Se1* locus with neighboring loci in rice

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The *Se 1* locus, which is located on chromosome 6, is a major locus controlling photoperiod sensitivity in rice. It has multiple alleles that adapt to different daylengths ranging from southern to northern latitudes. The *Se 1* locus is linked with the phosphoglucose isomerase isozyme (*Pgi2*) and blast resistance gene (*Pi-z'*) (Yokoo and Fujimaki 1971, Oosumi et al 1989).

This study was undertaken to find restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers linked closely to the *Se 1* gene and to construct the linkage map of *Se 1* with *Pi-z'*, *Pgi2*, and RFLP markers.

Four near-isogenic lines (NILs) were used as the crossing parents and developed as follows. A Japanese early variety, Fujisaka 5, was crossed with an indica variety Morak Sepilai from Malaysia. Fujisaka 5 was then backcrossed four times to the hybrids. The BC₄F₁ was selfed up to the BC₄F₁₃ generation by selecting the heterozygotes for heading time and blast resistance. Both an early-heading plant (Se-1^e/Se-1^e) and late-heading plant (Se-1^l/Se-1^l) that segregate for blast resistance were selected from the BC₄F₁₄ population. In the following generation, blast-resistant lines (*Pi-z'/Pi-z'*) and blast-susceptible lines (+/+) were obtained from each of early- and late-heading lines (Yokoo 1983) and designated as ER, ES, LR, and LS, respectively. In addition, ES, ER, and LS lines derived the *Pgi2* allele 1 from Fujisaka 5 while LR carried allele 2 from Morak Sepilai.

The F₂ plants of LR/ES and ER/LS were sown in the field on 29 Apr 1992 at the University of Tsukuba (36° N). The heading time of each plant was recorded as

the date when the first panicle emerged. The genotypes of F₂ plants, in which the heading time was not clear, were estimated by investigating segregation of the heading time of F₃ progenies in 1993. The genotypes of blast resistance in two populations were determined from the segregation of F₃ progenies in the blast nursery field. About 30 plants of each line at the fifth or sixth leaf stage were inoculated with a spore suspension of blast fungus strain 007. Blast resistance was scored 3 wk after inoculation.

The DNAs of parents and NILs were extracted from leaves by the CTAB method and were hybridized with rice genomic clones (RFLP markers) previously mapped to chromosome 6 (Saito et al 1991). Two of the 22 RFLP markers showed polymorphism among NILs. The DNA of 206 F₂ plants were extracted from leaves after heading and were digested with a restriction enzyme (*EcoRV*). Southern blot analysis was carried out to determine the RFLP genotypes of F₂ plants by using these two clones (XNpb 294, XNpb 233). Recombination values were calculated by MAPL program (Ukai et al 1990) based on maximum likelihood.

The segregation of heading time in two F₂ populations, LR/ES and ER/LS showed trimodal distributions, respectively, and fit well to a 1:2:1 (early:medium:late) ratio, indicating clear monogenic segregation of *Se 1* alleles. The phenotypic segregation of *Pi-z'* gene showed a good fit to the expected ratio (1:2:1) in two F₂ populations. The recombination values between *Se 1* and *Pi-z'* were 1.2 ± 0.4 in LR/ES and 1.2 ± 0.6 in ER/LS.

We analyzed *Pgi2* in the F₂ population of LR/ES. The segregation for the genotype of *Pgi2* fit well to the expected ratio (1:2:1) and showed the close linkage of *Pgi2* and *Se 1*. The recombination value was calculated as 2.8 ± 0.6.

Two RFLP markers (XNpb 294 and XNpb 233) revealed that only the LS line showed the identical band with the recurrent parent Fujisaka 5. The band of the other three lines was similar to that of the donor parent Morak Sepilai. The RFLP analysis was carried out for the F₂ population of ER/LS by using XNpb 294 and XNpb 233 as probes. The segregation of

The linkage map of *Pgi2*, *Se1*, *Pi-z'*, and two RFLP markers on chromosome 6 in rice. All distances are given in centimorgan units.

these two markers fit well to Mendelian monogenic inheritance. These markers were found to be tightly linked to *Se 1* and *Pi-z'* genes. The recombination value between XNpb 294 and *Se 1* was 3.7 ± 1.0 and that between XNpb 294 and *Pi-z'* was 2.5 ± 0.8. The recombination between XNpb 294 and XNpb 233 was not detected.

The linkage map was arranged from recombination values (see figure). Based on these results, *Pgi2*, XNpb 294, and XNpb 233 may be useful as molecular markers of the *Se 1* gene for genetic and breeding studies. However, molecular markers more tightly linked must be identified to clone the *Se 1* gene using map-based cloning procedures.

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